

PATHOGENETIC ASPECTS OF NAFLD THERAPY IN METABOLIC SYNDROME

¹Aripkhodjaye F.Z., ²Aripkhodjaye F.A

^{1,2}Alfraganus university Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Studies have been carried out to study the parameters of the functional state of the liver during short-term and long-term within three months of monotherapy with Rosuvastatin and combined therapy with Rosuvastatin and Jetepar in patients with NASH on the background of MS. Along with the positive dynamics in the parameters of the lipid spectrum, side effects of the drug Rosuvastatin on the functional state of the liver were revealed. Combined therapy with Rosuvastatin and Jetepar in NASH patients on the background of MS in the 3-month regimen, along with the positive dynamics of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, contributes to the normalization of ALT in 31%, AST in 40%, bilirubin in 25% and GGTP in 33% of patients.*

Keywords: *insulin resistance, steatohepatitis, metabolic syndrome.*

Introduction. Metabolic syndrome (MS) is increasingly becoming a serious medical and social problem due to the widespread increase in morbidity. Conducted population and clinical studies have proved that non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a hepatic manifestation of MS[21, 22]. NAFLD occupies the first position in the structure of chronic liver diseases among the Caucasian race and the second position among the etiological causes of liver cirrhosis worldwide [5, 24, 25]. The global prevalence of NAFLD is 25-34%, which, according to some authors, is characterized as a pandemic[25]. The leading components of MSCA, insulin resistance and dyslipidemia, are risk factors for the development of NAFLD and its progression on the one hand, and they are also serious predictors of cardiovascular morbidity (CVD), the mortality from which occupies a leading position in the world [5]. In 30% of patients diagnosed with NAFLD at the stage of steatosis and steatohepatitis, progression to steatofibrosis and steatocirrhosis is observed within 5-10 years. Fatal complications of portal hypertension develop in 25% of patients at the cirrhotic stage within the next 3 years [13]. Correction of the lipid profile in patients with NAFLD is an important part of therapy, as it reduces the risk of developing cardiovascular pathology and associated mortality. The accepted standard of treatment for dyslipidemia is the use of lipid-lowering drugs. According to the recommendations of EASL-EASD-EASO, statins can be used as part of NAFLD therapy to correct associated dyslipidemia and reduce the risk of adverse CVD (B1) [18]. Statins are recommended as first-line drugs for patients with elevated LDL cholesterol [2]. The positive opinion of statin group drugs in patients with NAFLD has been noted by many authors [3, 1, 8, 9, 6]. Numerous studies have shown the important role of statins in the treatment of dyslipidemia due to their ability to significantly reduce overall and coronary mortality [11]. However, the detection of the toxic effect of this group of drugs on the liver and the muscular system, an increase in transaminase activity was reflected in the recommendations of the All-Russian Scientific Society of Cardiology, where the use of statins is contraindicated or recommended to suspend the use of 2N ALT [12]. The mechanism of the adverse effect of statins on the functional state of the liver (FSP) is explained by the characteristic of a given group of drugs by the peculiarity of drug metabolism in the liver. The liver converts statins from inactive lactones

into the active form. At the same time, statins inhibit the synthesis of HMG-CoA reductase in hepatocytes, which is manifested by the cytotoxic properties of the drug [4].

Theoretically, the NAFLD therapy program provides not only for improving the functional state of the liver and preventing the development of liver fibrosis, but also in parallel should help reduce the atherogenic potential of the lipid spectrum to prevent the development of cardiovascular complications. The use of hepatoprotectors as an accompaniment therapy has found wide application in the clinical practice of NAFLD treatment. In the guidelines of the countries of the Asia-Pacific region, EASL, Italy, China and the USA, some drugs with cytoprotective activity are included in the list of standard therapy for NAFLD [17, 14, 15]. Thus, studies by some authors [23] have shown the positive effect of ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) in combination with lipid-lowering therapy, which reduced the risk of side effects from the liver. Some studies [2, 17] provide two and three component hepatoprotective therapy, depending on the functional state of the liver, to address the issues of long-term therapy. Therefore, given the pathogenetic validity of the use of statins in the complex therapy of NAFLD in MS, the improvement and development of hepatoprotective therapy with an emphasis on the main components of MS is an urgent task of practical healthcare.

Among the medicines of the new generation, the drug Jetepar attracts attention, showing psychotropic, antioxidant, antitoxic and cytoprotective effects. Betaine glucuronate, which is one of the components of the drug, performs the function of an acetyl-CoA carboxylase co-enzyme used by hepatocytes for beta-carboxylation of fatty acids, and also performs the function of a methyl group donor for the synthesis of choline and other amino alcohols. Another component of the drug, ascorbic acid, is a catalyst for redox reactions that promote the synthesis of chemical energy sources (ATP, UTP, etc.). Another component of the drug, nicotinamide, is an integral part of the NADH/NAD⁺ coenzyme, which also plays an important role in the biotransformation and detoxification of toxic substances. Numerous studies conducted abroad [16, 20] have shown sufficient efficacy of betaine glucuronate monotherapy in non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.

The purpose of this study was to study the effect of short-term and long-term use of the drug hypolipidemic action of rosuvastatin in the form of monotherapy and accompanied by hepatoprotector jetepar on the clinical and laboratory course of NAFLD in MS.

Materials and methods of research. Studies were conducted in 67 patients with NAFLD at the stage of NASH at the age of 26 to 72 years. Of these, 20 were men (30%) and 47 were women (70%). For the diagnosis of MS, the definition of the expert commissions of the US National Cholesterol Committee (ATP III – National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III) 2001 and the International Diabetes Federation (IFD) 2005 was used [19].

All patients underwent anthropometric studies: Body mass index (BMI) (Quetelet index) was calculated in relation to MT in kg to height in m² according to the formula ($BMI = m/p^2$, where m is human MT (kg), p is height (m)); coronary heart disease (CHD) was diagnosed based on anamnesis, physical and instrumental examination and ECG changes (typical for angina pectoris). The diagnosis of hypertension is based on the recommendation of the European Society of Hypertension and the European Society of Cardiology (2007).

The diagnosis of NAFLD is based on the study of factors of heredity, clinical, laboratory and liver ultrasound data. The criteria for exclusion from the study were: the presence of a factor of systematic alcohol consumption, the identification of markers of chronic viral hepatitis B, C

and Delta, and patients with autoimmune hepatitis against the background of the use of hormonal drugs.

Laboratory studies have been conducted to study the parameters of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism. Determination of the concentration of total cholesterol (OH), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL cholesterol), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL cholesterol), triglyceride (TG), glucose level, gammaglutamine transpeptidase (GGT), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), total bilirubin, albumin concentration, C-reactive protein (CRP), apolipoprotein AI (Apo A-I), apolipoprotein B (Apo B) in blood serum were carried out using reagent kits from BioSistemas (Spain) based on the enzymatic colorimetric method on an autoanalyzer (Mindray). Fasting insulin concentration was determined using AccuBingElisa reagents (USA) using the ELISA method. The severity of insulin resistance (IR) was assessed using the HOMA-IR hemostasis assessment model according to the formula: $HOMA-IR = \text{fasting glucose (mmol/l)} \times \text{fasting insulin (MED/ml)} / 22.5$. According to the recommendations of EASL-EASD-EASO (A1), the assessment of the severity of liver steatosis was determined by ultrasound (Mindray).

The treatment groups of patients with NAFLD were divided into 2 groups: 1 group of patients received the lipid-lowering drug rosuvastatin 20mg per day for 3 months; 2 group of patients received the lipid-lowering drug Rosuvastatin 20mg in combination with hepato-protector jetepar 10ml in a physical solution intravenously for 10 days monthly for 3 months. The control group consisted of 20 healthy donors.

The results of the study. The results of the conducted studies showed that in all examined patients the BMI was increased and amounted to 31.1 ± 0.70 kg/m² in men and 31.7 ± 0.45 kg/m² in women. Hypertension of stage I-II was detected in 20 (13%) men and 38 (25%) women. IHD was diagnosed in 18 (12%) men and 43 (28%) women. Type 2 diabetes mellitus was diagnosed in 15 (10%) men and 41 (27%) women.

The clinical characteristics of NASH patients manifested themselves in the form of general weakness and fatigue during physical exertion in 59 (88%) patients, blunt pain in the right hypochondrium in 32 (48%), dyspeptic manifestations after eating in 43 (64%) patients. According to ultrasound data, hepatomegaly was detected in 39 (58%) patients. Fatty liver dystrophy (a symptom of a "bright liver") was detected in all patients.

In the group of patients with monotherapy, the initial state of hyperbilirubinemia was manifested in 11 (35%), an increase in ALT levels within 1.5 – 2 norms was manifested in 25 (81%), AST - in 21 (68%), GGTP - in 18 (58%) patients. In the group of patients with combination therapy, an increase in bilirubin was detected in 13 (36%) patients, ALT - in 28 (78%), AST - in 21 (58%) and an increase in the concentration of intrahepatic cholestasis index – GGTPu - in 22 (61%). One of the main indicators of hepatic cell insufficiency – a decrease in albumin concentration was detected in 25 (81%) patients of the monotherapy group and 28 (78%) patients of combination therapy. The indicator of the mesenchymal inflammatory process – the concentration of C – reactive protein (CRP) was revealed in all patients of both groups compared.

The initial laboratory parameters of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism and indicators of the functional state of the liver in both groups of patients compared did not significantly differ from each other. (Table 1,2,3). At the same time, the indicators of NASH patients in both compared groups significantly differed from those of healthy individuals. Thus, the concentration of OH, TG, and Apo significantly ($P < 0.05$) differed in both groups compared with those of healthy people

(Table 1). Dyslipidemia was found in all patients with varying degrees of severity, which was manifested by a significant ($P<0.05$) increase in LDL, Apo B and a decrease in HDL, Apo A1. This was reflected in a significant increase in KA in both groups compared to healthy individuals. Indicators of the glycemc profile of sugar and insulin concentrations exceeded those of healthy people by an average of 1.6 and 4 times, respectively, which was reflected in significantly ($P<0.05$) increased HOMA index values (Table 2).

Table 1.

Indicators of the lipid spectrum of patients with NASH

Biochemical parameters	Healthy, n=20	Before treatment, n=31 n=36	After the first course of treatment, n=31 n=36	After the third course of treatment, n=31 n=36
Total cholesterol, mmol/l	4,4±0,19	<u>7,5±0,42*</u> 7,1±0,41*	<u>6,34±0,36*</u> $P<0,05$ 5,31±0,30* $P<0,05$	<u>5,28±0,30</u> $P<0,05$ <u>4,34±0,22</u> $P<0,05$
Triglycerides, mmol/l	1,42±0,07	<u>2,01±0,12*</u> 2,2±0,12*	<u>1,74±0,10*</u> $P>0,05$ 1,85±0,11* $P<0,05$	<u>1,43±0,09</u> $P<0,05$ <u>1,42±0,09</u> $P<0,05$
HDL, mmol/l	2,2±0,07	<u>1,12±0,06*</u> 1,05±0,06*	<u>1,32±0,07*</u> $P>0,05$ 1,26±0,07* $P<0,05$	<u>1,62±0,08*</u> $P<0,05$ 1,62±0,08* $P<0,05$
LDL, mmol/l	2,6±0,12	<u>3,94±0,20*</u> 3,84±0,20*	<u>2,74±0,15</u> $P<0,05$ <u>2,59±0,13</u> $P<0,05$	<u>2,42±0,13</u> $P<0,05$ <u>2,05±0,11</u> $P<0,05$
CA	1,05±0,12	<u>6,7±0,71*</u> 6,8±0,72*	<u>4,14±0,49*</u> $P<0,05$ 3,77±0,41* $P<0,05$	<u>2,21±0,29*</u> $P<0,05$ 1,93±0,22* $P<0,05$
Apolipoprotein A1, g/l	193,5±9,28	<u>151,6±8,93*</u> 149,1±8,21*	<u>170,9±9,24</u> $P>0,05$ 179,4±9,27 $P<0,05$	<u>191,6±10,1</u> $P<0,05$ 215,2±11,4 $P<0,05$
Apolipoprotein B	86,7±3,35	<u>170,7±9,65*</u> 174,9±8,98*	<u>143,4±7,9*</u> $P<0,05$ 143,3±7,33* $P<0,05$	<u>114,3±6,4*</u> $P<0,05$ 111,9±5,8* $P<0,05$
Atherogenicity index	0,47±0,03	<u>1,27±0,11*</u> <u>1,33±0,12*</u>	<u>0,92±0,07*</u> $P<0,05$ 0,88±0,07* $P<0,05$	<u>0,65±0,05*</u> $P<0,05$ 0,58±0,05 $P<0,05$

Note: In the numerator, the indicators of patients who received monotherapy; in the denominator, the indicators of patients who received combination therapy; * - the presence of a significant difference from healthy individuals; P<0.05 – the presence of a significant difference before treatment; P>0.05 – the absence of a significant difference before treatment

Table 2.

Indicators of the glycemc profile of patients with NASH

Biochemical parameters	Healthy, n=20	Before treatment, n=31 n=36	After the first course of treatment, n=31 n=36	After the third course of treatment, n=31 n=36
Fasting sugar, mmol/l	4,11±0,16	<u>6,5±0,49*</u> 6,5±0,36*	<u>5,8±0,45*</u> P>0,05 5,8±0,32* P>0,05	<u>5,4±0,37*</u> P<0,05 5,4±0,29* P<0,05
Fasting insulin, MED/ml	11,7±0,51	<u>46,6±2,43*</u> 52,1±2,75*	<u>38,4±2,08*</u> P<0,05 35,7±1,88* P<0,05	<u>31,3±1,74*</u> P<0,05 24,2±1,19* P<0,05
HOMA Index	2,12±0,11	<u>12,5±0,71</u> 14,1±0,72*	<u>9,3±0,6*</u> P<0,05 8,7±0,42* P<0,05	<u>7,01±0,43*</u> P<0,05 5,4±0,24* P<0,05

Note: In the numerator, the indicators of patients who received monotherapy; in the denominator, the indicators of patients who received combination therapy; * - the presence of a significant difference from healthy individuals; P<0.05 – the presence of a significant difference before treatment; P>0.05 – the absence of a significant difference before treatment

Table 3.

Indicators of the functional state of the liver of patients with NASH

Biochemical parameters	Healthy, n=20	Before treatment, n=31 n=36	After the first course of treatment, n=31 n=36	After the third course of treatment, n=31 n=36
Bilir. total, mmol/l	15,88±0,84	<u>20,9±1,45*</u> 19,7±1,06	<u>21,8±1,42*</u> P>0,05 19,7±1,06 P>0,05	<u>20,9±1,23*</u> P>0,05 17,8±0,81 P>0,05
ALT, UNITS/l	17,5±2,5	<u>70,1±4,58*</u> 68,6±4,8*	<u>80,6±4,72*</u> P>0,05 60,2±4,29* P>0,05	<u>108,8±5,75*</u> P<0,05 43,4±3,09 P<0,05
AST, UNITS /l	12,7±2,2	<u>39,6±2,47*</u> 41,9±2,90*	<u>46,2±3,13*</u> P>0,05 31,7±2,23* P<0,05	<u>77,9±4,23*</u> P<0,05 5 24,5±1,41 P<0,05
GGTP, UNITS/l	22,8±1,05	<u>70,0±4,02*</u> 69,2±4,74*	<u>78,5±4,52*</u> P>0,05 53,8±3,96* P<0,05	<u>113,6±6,38*</u> P<0,05 38,7±2,68* P<0,05

Total protein, g/l	69,3±1,98	<u>67,5±2,02</u>	<u>65,5±1,94</u> ^{P>0,05}	<u>64,8±2,01</u> ^{P>0,05}
		66,1±1,84	68,0±1,80 ^{P>0,05}	72,1±1,82 ^{P<0,05}
Albumin, %	51,9±1,84	<u>42,1±1,45*</u>	<u>40,2±1,64*</u> ^{P>0,05}	<u>36,3±1,50*</u> ^{P<0,05}
		40,9±1,36	44,7±1,43 ^{P>0,05}	53,4±1,55 ^{P<0,05}
CRP, cu/e	2,45±0,26	<u>9,6±0,6*</u>	<u>8,9±0,56*</u> ^{P>0,05}	<u>7,7±0,61*</u> ^{P<0,05}
		10,4±0,56	6,9±0,40 ^{P<0,05}	4,53±0,27 ^{P<0,05}

Note: In the numerator, the indicators of patients who received monotherapy; in the denominator, the indicators of patients who received combination therapy; * - the presence of a significant difference from healthy individuals; P<0.05 – the presence of a significant difference before treatment; P>0.05 – the absence of a significant difference before treatment

The results of the dynamics of lipid spectrum indices against the background of the use of rosuvastatin by the end of the first month showed a significant (P<0.05) decrease in the concentration of atherogenic lipid fractions – OH, LDL, APO B, KA, with a statistically insignificant decrease in TG levels (Table 1). There were also no significant differences in the concentration of antiatherogenic fractions of HDL lipids, APO A1 compared to the initial indicators. We revealed the unidirectional nature of the dynamics of OH, LDL, on the one hand, and the fasting insulin index, the NOME index, on the other, by the end of monthly therapy (Table 2). At the same time, we did not detect a significant (P>0.05) decrease in sugar levels. The study of the indicators of the functional state of the liver in this period showed the absence of statistically significant dynamics of a decrease in bilirubin, albumin and CRP with a tendency (P>0.05) to increase ALT, AST, GGTP, however, these changes were not significant (Table 3).

Dynamic follow-up of patients on the background of three-month monotherapy showed positive dynamics (P<0.05) in lipid profile parameters - OH, TG, LDL, APO B. At the same time, a significant increase (P<0.05) in HDL and APO A1 was revealed, which was reflected in a significant (P<0.05) decrease in KA (Table 1). A similar dynamics was revealed in terms of glycemic profile, which confirms the pathogenetic relationship of insulin resistance with dyslipidemia (Table 2). In terms of the functional state of the liver, we revealed a significant (P<0.05) increase in GGTP levels with a significant (P<0.05) decrease in albumin concentration, which may be due to the effect of the metabolic load of prolonged rosuvastatin therapy on liver function, while 22 (71%) patients of this group had complaints of weakness and fatigue. We have not identified any clinical symptoms of cholestatic syndrome activation. We revealed a significant (P<0.05) increase in ALT, AST, and GGTP compared to the baseline level (Table 3). It should be noted that a decrease in the level of ALT, AST and GGTP in patients with initially elevated indicators was not revealed, which once again confirms the need for supportive therapy of the functional state of the liver in this contingent.

Analysis of laboratory parameters of patients who received combination therapy by the end of the first month showed positive dynamics of lipid and glycemic profile indicators (Table 1). Thus, we revealed a decrease in OH, TG, LDL, APO B, KA by 1.3; 1.2; 1.5; 1.2; 1.8 times, respectively, compared with the indicators before treatment. Indicators of the glycemic profile – sugar, fasting insulin, as well as the NOME index decreased by 1.2; 1.5; 1.6 times (Table 2). It should be noted a significant (P<0.05) decrease in CRP as an indicator of the mesenchymal inflammatory process and the progression of liver fibrosis. Against the background of combination therapy, we revealed positive dynamics in terms of bilirubin, ALT, AST, GGTP, however, these

indicators remained significantly high compared to those of healthy individuals. (Table 3). Analysis of laboratory studies by the end of three months of therapy showed a significant ($P<0.05$) decrease in OH, TG, LDL, APO by 1.6; 1.5; 1.8; 1.6 times, with a statistically significant ($P<0.05$) increase in HDL and APO A1 (1.5; 1.4 times, respectively). This was reflected by a 3.5 fold decrease in KA. However, these indicators remained significantly high ($P<0.05$) compared with those of healthy people (Table 1). By the end of therapy, we revealed a significant ($P<0.05$) decrease in sugar, fasting insulin, and the NOME index by 1.2; 2.1; 2.6 times, the values of which also remained significantly high ($P<0.05$) compared with the healthy cohort (Table 2). Analysis of biochemical parameters of the functional state of the liver by the end of three months of therapy showed normalization of ALT in 31% of patients, AST in 40%, bilirubin in 25% and GGTP in 33% of patients. Normalization of the indicator of the mesenchymal inflammatory process of CRP was detected in 75% of patients. We should note the positive effect of combination therapy on the indicators of hepatic cell insufficiency, which manifested itself in a significant ($P<0.05$) increase in albumin concentration (Table 3).

Discussion. It is known that the issue of studying NAFLD, which includes a violation of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism in its pathogenesis, is relevant primarily in terms of the prevention of cardiovascular complications. According to some authors, the high risk of developing atherosclerosis [10] increases in the presence of inflammatory factors. The initially detected elevated markers of hepatocyte cytolysis-ALT, AST, and the indicator of the mesenchymal inflammatory process of the liver- are obviously factors of activation of subclinical inflammation. This undoubtedly has a pathogenetic relationship with the process of activation of vascular atherogenesis, therefore it will be reflected in the dynamics of indicators of metabolic syndrome. The inclusion of the drug Jetepar with an antioxidant effect and the property of correcting beta-carboxylation of fatty acids in hepatocytes, in our opinion, affects the leading mechanisms of NAFLD. The positive dynamics of liver functional parameters during the combined therapy with the use of the drug Rosuvastatin once again confirms the possibility of using Jetepar as a pathogenetically based hepatoprotective therapy. Analyzing the work experience of some researchers on the effective use of hepato-protector acodeoxycholic acid in NASH for up to 12 months [7, 23] or essential phospholipids for up to 6months 4-5 [8, 9, 14], the long-term use of the proposed combination therapy should obviously be decided individually with each patient, depending on the dynamics of laboratory parameters.

Conclusions.

1. Combination therapy of the lipid-lowering drug Rosuvastatin in combination with the hepato-protector Jetepar contributes to the normalization of cytolytic, mesenchymal inflammatory liver syndrome and has a positive effect on the dynamics of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism in patients with NASH on the background of MS.

2. The use of the hepato-protector Jetepar, while maintaining the functional parameters of the liver, makes it possible to use prolonged schemes of lipid-lowering therapy in patients with NASH on the background of MS.

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